

Report for Kiel-Gdańsk Market Place in Kiel 2022

1.1. Expectations at the beginning of the pilot activity

This pilot activity **“Kieler Marktplatz” (Market Place Event)** of Kiel University is an event to enable exchange between scientists and business people, based on presentations and discussions about actual topics. The networking character provides contacts for future cooperation and commercialization of inventions. Two such events were planned to be organized. The first event was taking place as a Kiel-Gdańsk Market Place on May 31st 2022 in Kiel.

The Kieler Market Place is born by the idea of cooperation and sharing of knowledge between science and business related to marine topics. Pooling people, support their interaction and lead them to their most correlating overlap in topic is the main focus of the project. This kind of event is already established on the local level in Kiel, basing on the cooperation of Kiel university and the Maritime Cluster Norther Germany.

The proposal is basing on the intention to bring this event format to an international level, implemented by organizing an event in cooperation with an international partner. The importance of dealing with in particular autonomous shipping and in general marine related topics, does not matter from which perspective, should not be limited within the borders of Germany rather on international grounds.

The University of Gdańsk showed up as the perfectly fitting partner for the first international Kiel Market Place due to the facts that Gdańsk has a maritime industry as well as the university represents a strong interested in increasing technology transfer and business cooperation.

Poster of Kiel-Gdańsk Market Place 2022

The vision of this pilot activity was co-designing, co-creating and co-delivering knowledge with and for stakeholders of science and business in context of autonomous shipping. Creating contacts for future cooperation and commercialization of inventions within the frame of smart harbour and smart shipping in dependence on autonomous shipping.

The university Gdańsk figured out to be experts in smart ships – smart harbours and fit perfectly in the concept of the international Kiel-Gdańsk Market Place. The Kiel-Gdańsk Market Place appeared with a dynamic day program including a theoretical part (presentations, discussion round), a more practical part (visit of the wavelab at FH Kiel, University of Applied Sciences) and ended up in a loosened networking dinner. The possibilities of cooperation and sharing thoughts as well as knowledge was supported by the structure of the program.

1.2. Methodology and Development

The team of Kiel met up regularly once or twice a month. The idea was:

- Collecting of thoughts, ideas, experiences and knowledge from every single Kieler Marketplace member regarding the potential of topics, knowing of prominent experts possibly fitting in this project format.
- Visualizing the possibilities and outcome of extending the Kieler Market Place to an international version based on the previous experiences of the last Kieler Market Places.

In the end the event was planned in small steps.

- a) Collecting and selecting recent possible topics
- b) Milestone decision: Topic of the event - “smart shipping”
- c) Milestone decision: Becoming partner - the University of Gdańsk

Since then: virtual meetings were set up for following progress

- d) Evaluation of possible experts of autonomous shipping from Kiel as well as from Gdańsk side
- e) Milestone decision: CAPTN as main actor and focus project
Complemented by presentations about recent research and perspectives from Gdańsk side
- f) Development of infrastructure for the event: location, technical information for participants, application format, etc.
- g) Meanwhile program format in steady progress: (theoretical) presentation part, (practical) visits of port of Kiel and the wavelab at FH Kiel, networking in dinner atmosphere
Meanwhile evaluation of potential participants of business branch, politics and others

The possibilities of cooperation and sharing thoughts as well as knowledge was supported by the structure of the program.

The methodology employed for the completion of this pilot action were steady updates and progress towards the implementation of the event format via e-mail and virtual meetings.

The communication was split in two: 1st internal Kiel as hosts, 2nd Gdańsk + Kiel for the extended communication.

Work and meetings conducted in reference to this deliverable/ milestone:

- 1) Already established core team of the Kiel Market Place Event since 2008: Christian-Albrecht-University (CAU) - Kiel Marine Science (KMS), Wissenschaftszentrum Kiel (WiZe), Martimes Cluster Norddeutschland (MCN).
- 2) Decision about the first international Kieler Market Place
- 3) 19.11.2021 – first contact with the University of Gdańsk as international partner

Brainstorm and decision making within following virtual meetings:

- 13 January 2022 – decision-making process about the topic: “Smart shipping”
- 01 March 2022 – possible event format including scientific presentations from Kiel and Gdańsk speakers, discussion, possible site visit of port (and others), preparation of first draft program, first thoughts about possible invitations and speakers, infrastructural process from Kiel side (location, transport, catering etc.).
- 09 March 2022 – event date 31 May 2022, a one day event, final decision of the topic: “smart shipping - smart ship, smart harbour” (main topic with two subtopics), distribution of talks; creational program progress, including talks, visits, networking, personal interaction
- 16 March 2022 – decision about talks and the main speakers Kiel: CAPTN initiative; Gdańsk: University Gdańsk and Baltic Sea & Space Cluster, clarifying participation list
- 12 April 2022 – progress of program, technical information, final participants list, finalisation of program
- 07 July 2022 – Feedback meeting Kiel internal
- 08 July 2022 – Feedback meeting Kiel-Gdańsk and reSEArch-EU

1.3. Challenges found and solution proposed

The main difficulties were:

- a) to reach all members in time, to achieve a steady response frequency and hold everyone on the same page with steady progress

- b) the application format could have been better organized. Some people were not able to join due to the assumption of a day event and no option of joining partwise.
- c) less external participant appeared than expected from Gdańsk side, what resulted in a less bi-national exchange
- d) the presence of external experts and participants appeared inconstant, what created the exchange more difficult.

The task force got over these obstacles found along the way by talking and finding solutions between the organizers. Focusing on experiences and profession of every member.

If starting this pilot activity all over again, the following would be done differently:

- regarding b): application possibilities for single program blocks (morning, midday, evening), earlier opening of the application tool.
- regarding c): more commitment with the application as well as more input in the network with business partners.
- regarding d): more involvement of externals from our side as host, more proactive initiation of possibly good fitting contacts between all participants. A format with more commitment.

1.4. Results obtained

30 persons, thereof 16 stakeholders, participated in the in-person event that offered presentations in the morning and visiting trips in the afternoon. Participants from science and business were able to inform, exchange and discuss the topic of smart shipping from different perspectives. During the discussion, it was possible to figure out some pro and cons of autonomous shipping as well as borders in implementation.

The external Gdańsk perspective and needs were clearly articulated as well as the possible option for support each other what appeared especially in further networking through different institutions.

It was possible to underline the theoretical information during the talks with already implemented modelling structures at the university of applied sciences as well as applications in the port of Kiel.

Wave lab at university of applied sciences in Kiel with a model of a autonomous ferry by CAPTN.

Port of Kiel with an already implemented land power station.

Recently active data collection on the Kiel fjord ferry could be witnessed, as well as the experience of the already developing technic from the Kiel fjord ferries from combustion engine to the new e-engine, respectively hybrid engine.

This action has been beneficial for the project partners individually. From Kiel perspective, an overview of the work in Gdańsk according to smart shipping respectively autonomous shipping could be obtained. Exchange of thoughts and critical discussion about the implementation and further success were very valuable.

Discussion round

For the consortium this action was beneficial as the experiences and methodologies will be included in the final report in the end of December 2023.

1.5. Quality Self-Assessment

This activity is contributing to two transformation modules from the proposal, the transformation modul (4): reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially the academia-business cooperation; and the transformation modul (6) involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation.

This event contributed to strengthen business-academia partnerships, which is one of the key priorities of the reSEArch-EU project aiming at maximising the local/regional and global competitiveness. With the example of the CAPTN initiative on autonomous shipping in Kiel, the importance of place-based innovation ecosystems was shown to be critical to enable university, industry and the small and medium-sized enterprises in reaching their full potential. CAPTN is

an excellent example of a strong regional cooperation, which could be presented to the visitors from Gdańsk.

Also the activity was in strong relation to Transformation modul (6): Both Kiel and Gdańsk are located in coastal regions that share strong geographical, historical and social similarities. They are regions that have always been characterised by a high mobility of goods and people. By the Market Place activity, smart shipping was clearly shown as an important approach to develop a sustainable future mobility in both cities.

The quality of the result could have been better, if the number of participants had been raised by spending more time in the outreach of the project reasoned in the fact that high mobility of goods and people are concerning all of us. Furthermore, the event could even be made more attractive to share knowledge, support the creation of research issues and transformation practice in any cases through high motivation and inspiring perspectives.

The results obtained could be further exploited and sustained over time by steady updates of the development from the perspective of all stakeholders' interests within their market needs and scientific progress and by catching up with individual changes in needs. Frequently getting together for being in touch in person for deepening a longterm attachment would be contributing, beside a general support of networking and transformation processes.

Group of experts of the Kiel-Gdańsk-Marketplace 2022.

1.6. Kiel Market Place in Kiel 2023

Another Market Place Event (“Kieler Marktplatz”) took place in Kiel on 22 April 2023, however unlike the year before, without the participation of any project alliance partners due to the focus on a very regional topic about maritime critical infrastructures in Schleswig-Holstein/Germany.

46 partners from Kiel, thereof 36 stakeholder, participated in the event that was held in German language.